

Original Article

Relationship Between Learning Styles, Listening Proficiency Level, and Intensity of Watching YouTube Videos: A Case of Undergraduate Students in Private Universities of Karachi

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between learning styles, listening proficiency level, and intensity of watching YouTube videos of students. The researcher employed a quantitative and correlational method. To investigate the listening proficiency level and learning styles of students, IELTS listening sample test was used. To gain more insight into students' practice of watching YouTube videos, a quantitative questionnaire (Likert Scale) comprised of five questions was distributed among the students. A sample of a hundred students was randomly selected to collect data. The correlation between the variables was analyzed by using SPSS and the correlation was found. The results of the study depict that there is a positive correlation between students' intensity of watching YouTube videos. However, there is a negative correlation between the learning styles of students and the intensity of watching YouTube Videos with insignificant p-value. The study recommends further investigation using different variables such as students' self-directed learning habits, the influence of guided YouTube usage, motivation, and access to technology. These elements could provide further light on the best ways to use multimedia platforms like YouTube for language learning.

Keywords: Learning Styles, Listening Proficiency, YouTube, Correlation, English Language

INTRODUCTION

With technological advancement, all human activities have been digitalized in one way or the other. Digital technologies have opened a new horizon for students by providing various opportunities to enhance their listening skills (Hassan et al., 2023). In this digital era, the process of English language teaching and learning is not limited to the classrooms only. The students are now more inclined to watch and listen to English YouTube videos for academic and non-academic purposes. YouTube videos seem interesting and entertaining to youngsters; moreover, they effectively enhance the student's listening skills (Ray et al., 2021). English has been used as a medium of instruction in native (Akinwamide, 2012; Mahboob, 2005) as well as non-English speaking countries such as Pakistan, Indonesia, and Malaysia (Mahboob, 2003) where most of the students do not have well-developed English language skills. The acquisition of English revolves around developing all four language skills i.e. listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Listening and speaking skills are considered the basic skills for language learning. However, listening and speaking skills have been completely ignored by the students and English language teachers in Pakistan (Hamouda, 2013; Maitlo, Tumrani & Ali, 2022; Mirza et al. 2021).

Moreover, ELT teachers in Pakistan merely focus on teaching and evaluating reading and writing skills (Kakar, & Zia, 2023). They perceive that the students will automatically acquire listening skills over time (Hamouda, 2013; Mirza et al. 2021). As English language skills are not widely practiced for communication purposes in the Pakistani context, this perception has proved to be a failure because students have very weak language skills (Hassan et al., 2023). According to educationalists, there are three learning styles: auditory, visual, and kinesthetic (Oxford, 2003). Cohen & Henry (2019) have maintained that variables such as learning methods, learning preferences, and

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motivation to acquire L2 play a crucial role in language acquisition. The L2 learners use a variety of strategies to improve their English Language skills. Studies on proficient language learners have shown that, in addition to students' motivation and language aptitude, L2 learners' active efforts and creativity in incorporating different strategies also play a vital role in language development. During COVID-19, the students have developed digital literacy abilities and transformed their learning styles to master listening-related metacognitive strategies (Arsyad & Villia, 2022).

Studies have depicted that computer-assisted learning is predominant in the English language context (Sauro, 2016). YouTube has developed into one of the most popular internet platforms in the world since its launch in 2005. As a result, studies exploring its integration in the L2 context have gained popularity (Dizon, 2022). Mayer's (1997) theory of multimedia learning, which is based on cognitive science, provides additional support for using YouTube for L2 learning. According to this idea, humans use two channels to process information: a visual channel that processes images or videos and an auditory or verbal channel that processes aural input. Although, L2 learners were not considered when the idea of multimedia learning was created. Preliminary research indicates that L2 English learners' listening comprehension is greatly improved when a video is added to an audio lecture (Mayer et al., 2014). In other words, using dual channels (auditory and visual) in contrast to a single channel seems to increase L2 comprehension, supporting the hypothesis of multimedia learning's relevance in L2 circumstances. Given these results, it is not unreasonable to assume that YouTube, which combines auditory and visual input, could enhance L2 processing more efficiently in contrast with the use of reading or listening in segregation (Dizon, 2022). A previous study in the form of a review (Khairat et al., 2024) also highlights the effective use of YouTube to improve English listening skills, supporting its growing role in language learning pedagogy.

Researchers such as Dizon (2023) have found that YouTube helps enhance English language development, level of motivation in the context of an authentic L2 English language learning environment, and intercultural learning. Dizon (2023) has strongly recommended research to study the effectiveness of watching YouTube videos on language development. The researcher has designed this current correlational study to fill the gap in the literature. The study would find out how the frequency of watching YouTube videos affects the listening proficiency level of undergraduate students and what relationship exists between the frequency of watching YouTube videos and the learning styles of undergraduate students. Listening skills are the most vital in language development and have been observed to be the most neglected skills in ESL classrooms. The findings of the study would be significant for both ESL teachers and students as it would highlight the importance of exploring the learning styles of L2 learners, assessing the current listening proficiency level of students, and incorporating the most appropriate teaching-learning strategies that satisfy the actual learning needs of the students (listening skills) according to their particular learning preferences. Moreover, the results would help ESL teachers and students by highlighting the impact of watching YouTube videos on developing the student's listening skills.

Research Objective

- To find out the correlation between students' learning styles, the amount of time spent watching YouTube videos, students and their current listening proficiency level

LITERATURE REVIEW

English Language Learning

English is currently the most powerful and international language in various parts of the world along with the national languages of regions, it has now become a passport to achieve the learning goals in education everywhere in the world regardless of culture, religion, or ethnic background (Khan & Mansoor, 2020). Pakistan's development of higher education and higher jobs depends on English as the primary language (Coleman, 2010; Rahman, 2002). Additionally, English is the only tool regarded as being responsible for the failure of most of the students in Pakistan (Bruthiaux, 2002). Due to the increase in the significance of English, it has become mandatory throughout Pakistan. This compulsion has created several issues for students with weak English language skills (Haider, 2018). According to some scholars, well-developed English language skills help students succeed in academic and professional careers (Haidar, 2019; Vaish, 2005). In addition to that, several components should be learned if the students wish to develop English language proficiency, these skills are listening, speaking, reading and writing (Putri & Ayu, 2023). According to Burns (2018), pupils should acquire four English competencies. These four abilities are crucial for both teaching and learning English. According to Morley (1991), listening is the most

frequent form of communication in daily life. Because it is the first ability we master while learning a language, we listen roughly twice as often as we speak, four times as much as we read, and five times as much as we write.

Listening Skills

In addition to teaching reading skills, teachers also need to develop the student's listening skills of students as they hold a crucial place in English language teaching and learning (Putri & Ayu, 2023). As explained by Ahmed (2015), five basic listening abilities need to be developed: Predicting content, listening for gist (finding the broad meaning), detecting signposts (understanding the subjects), listening for details (finding specific information), and inferring meaning (guessing the meaning). Similar arguments have been sustained by Nunan (1998) that listening skills are basic for language development, and without gaining competency in listening skills, students can never learn to communicate in L2 effectively.

Learning Styles and Listening Skills

To make the development of listening skills easy, teachers need to use the most suitable teaching strategies (Putri & Ayu, 2023). Learning styles are the distinctive ways people acquire, perceive, and process knowledge (Hilliard, 2020). Learning styles refer to a person's quickest and most effective learning. No doubt, every student has a unique learning style. Some pupils learn more quickly by seeing, others learn the best by hearing and listening, and some understand more by touching and moving. One of the key elements determining how and how well children learn a second language or a foreign language is their learning style, which can impact their reading, writing, listening, and speaking comprehension. It implies links between learning styles and English language learning exist (Putri & Ayu, 2023).

Factors that Influence Listening Skills

According to Norflee (2014), four factors that affect listening are:

The Listeners

The more listeners are interested in the topic, the easier it will be for them to listen to the topic discussed.

Background Knowledge

Without adequate background knowledge, listeners with poor listening skills will have difficulty accessing information.

Style of Speech

How people talk may affect listening. If people use speech fasting, listeners may have difficulty accepting the information they are trying to convey understanding.

Visual Input

For some people, visual support helps with listening to new information.

Fig. 1. An Overview of Factors

Watching YouTube Video

YouTube has developed into one of the most popular internet platforms in the world since its launch in 2005. As a result, studies exploring its use in formal and informal settings have gained popularity in second language (L2)

research. Many scholars have proved that watching YouTube videos is advantageous for several reasons (Aldukhayel, 2021; Alexa, 2022; Alobaid, 2020). One of which is related to language (Yassin, 2024).

Development of Language Skills

This reason is related to the current study. For instance, students in Sun and Fang (2015) stated that YouTube assisted their efforts to speak English more fluently and helped them spot linguistic weaknesses, particularly in L2 pronunciation. Aldukhayel's study participants believed that pronunciation improvement was one of the major benefits of watching YouTube videos or vlogs. It is also crucial to remember that the instructor participants in Aldukhayel (2021) shared the same viewpoint, namely that YouTube may aid students in honing their language-related abilities. Arndt and Woore (2018) discovered that although not to the same extent as those who read blogs, students who watched YouTube videos could improve their incidental vocabulary learning. Yaacob et al., (2021) discovered in another quantitative investigation that YouTube could improve young learners' listening comprehension. The results of these investigations show that YouTube has the potential to enhance language skills in many ways.

Watching YouTube Videos in Formal Settings

Benson's (2011) four aspects of language acquisition will be used to distinguish between formal and informal learning situations. According to this approach, formal L2 learning refers to language acquisition that is other-directed, such as by a teacher or researcher, that may happen in or outside the classroom. On the other hand, informal L2 learning refers to self-directed, outside-of-class, naturalistic language learning. The use of two Web 2.0 technologies (YouTube and Facebook) in a service-learning task-problem-based learning that revolves around providing a helpful service to the community—and L2 English students' perceptions of language improvements were examined by Sun and Yang (2015). While the participants' opinions were generally positive—they believed that YouTube helped them improve their public speaking abilities and L2 speaking confidence—it was also discovered that they spent more time on the aesthetic aspects of their videos than on the original learning objective.

Aldukhayel (2021) investigated the participants' opinions on YouTube for L2 learning and found that using YouTube videos in well-structured in-class activities could aid in developing L2 skills and make language instruction more engaging and real. Yaacob et al. (2021) investigated in action research if a YouTube-based approach that included video podcasts and associated listening exercises may improve young L2 English learners' listening comprehension. According to the findings, the therapy significantly impact the participants' listening comprehension. Woore (2018) used a quantitative, experimental strategy to study the impact of pre-testing on vocabulary evaluation. Participants were divided into two groups: one watched YouTube videos and the other read the transcripts. A test was used to determine if participants could accidentally learn target pseudo-words. Although no significant differences were found in overall vocabulary learning, the YouTube group outperformed the blog group in three areas related to vocabulary enhancement.

Watching YouTube Videos in Informal Settings

According to the limited knowledge of the researcher, only two studies have looked into the use of YouTube in casual L2 learning settings. The first is an exploratory study by Benson (2015) that examined YouTube comments to see if there were any indications of language learning or cross-cultural learning. 2,840 comments or 32% of the total (8,850 comments) showed signs of language or intercultural learning. These findings imply that informal foreign language learning can be found in great abundance in YouTube comments. Wang and Chen (2019) conducted interviews with university students to learn more about how they used and viewed L2 English YouTubers or content creators that particularly make videos for English-teaching objectives. The participants reported that they preferred watching YouTubers to deepen their knowledge of other cultures, broaden their access to learning resources, and spark interest in learning a second language.

Studies Conducted in the Pakistani Context

Ajmal & Kumar (2020) studied the impact of motivation on students' listening skills while studying in the British Education and Training System in Karachi, Pakistan from January to February 2020. According to the results, there is a positive correlation between listening strategy instruction and motivation. Naz, Simming, and Jarah (2022) conducted a qualitative experimental study in the Pakistani context and found that the use of Computer Assisted Language Learning had a positive impact on enhancing students' listening skills as compared to regular classroom teaching techniques. Asif, Sheeraz & Sacco (2022) conducted a quantitative experimental study to investigate the impact of technology tools and web-delivered language learning platforms on the academic

performance of L2 learners of the English language in the private university of Karachi, Pakistan. The results depicted a positive impact of technological tools on the academic performance of English language learners.

Abbasi, Shahid & Shah (2022) designed a quantitative study to explore the problems faced by L2 learners of non-elite private secondary schools in Punjab, Pakistan regarding listening comprehension skills. The study showed that students face difficulty in listening comprehension due to the lack of vocabulary, form of language, difficult grammatical structures, speed of language delivery, lack of interest, poor quality of sound, and problems related to the poor setting of classrooms. The researchers recommended that the curriculum developers must include technology-assisted material in the textbooks (Gurmani, 2022). Maitlo, Tumrani & Shoukat (2022) explored the factors that negatively affect the listening and speaking skills of L2 learners studying in secondary schools in Sindh, Pakistan. The study suggests that watching English language videos can help students improve their listening and speaking skills.

The Gap

The literature review depicts that scholars have studied the relationship between watching YouTube videos and students' listening comprehension skills from different perspectives by utilizing many different approaches and methodologies. However, a study that investigates the relationship between L2 learners' learning styles, the intensity of watching YouTube videos, and the students' listening proficiency level has been rarely found especially in the Pakistani context. Therefore, the current study would fill the knowledge gap in the literature and enlighten L2 instructors and students regarding the relationship between the learners' learning styles, watching YouTube videos, and the students' listening proficiency levels.

METHODOLOGY

A quantitative design has been utilized to fulfill the objective of the study. The population of this study was undergraduate students from private universities in Karachi. The researcher employed the probability sampling technique to draw a sample of a hundred undergraduate students from three private universities selected randomly. Three questionnaires were employed as tools to collect data from selected participants. The first tool was a questionnaire (five questions) related to students' preference to watch YouTube videos. The second tool was the VAK Learning Style Inventory developed by Chislett and Chapman (2005) to explore the students' learning styles. The third tool was the IELTS listening sample test to assess student's current listening proficiency levels. All these surveys are based on objective-type questions and MCQs.

Fig. 2. An Overview of Tools

Data Collection Process

The tests and the survey questionnaires were compiled in sets to be distributed to each student. The sets were numbered to keep a separate record of each student: use of YouTube videos, learning style, and proficiency level to further correlate the responses recorded by each student. All the data was collected on the same day. Firstly, the students were asked to fill out the VAK Learning Style Inventory to investigate the learning style of each student. Secondly, the IELTS Listening Test was conducted to investigate the students' current listening proficiency levels. Thirdly, the students were asked to fill out a survey questionnaire that provided data related to the use of YouTube videos by the students. In the end, the sets were collected back from all students. The collected data were correlated

through SPSS software to perform data analysis. The correlation was calculated among the variables i.e. time spent watching YouTube videos, students' learning styles, and students' current listening proficiency levels. The results have also been given in tables and charts to enhance comprehension of the findings.

RESULTS & FINDINGS

Data Description and Display

The data analysis part has been divided into two sections. In the first stage, the data is displayed in tables and charts along with their descriptions. The second stage deals with the explanation and interpretation of the data.

Chart Description: Frequency of Watching YouTube Videos

	Frequency	Percent
Daily	4	4
Several times a week	20	20
Once a week	28	28
Rarely	36	36
Never	12	12

The question related to the frequency of watching YouTube videos, prepared on a five-point rating scale i.e. daily, several times a week, once a week, rarely, and never. Most students (36%) informed that they rarely watch YouTube videos. However, only 4% claimed that they watch YouTube videos every day and others stated that they watch only once a week (28%), several times a week (20%) and 12% declared that they never watch YouTube videos. This shows that the participants do not benefit from YouTube videos for academic or non-academic purposes.

Chart Description: Intensity of Watching YouTube Videos

	Frequency	Percent
Less than a minute	48	48
30 minutes to 1 hour	40	40
1 to 2 hours	8	8
More than 2 hours	4	4

The response to this question deals with the intensity of watching YouTube videos. Most of the students (48%) responded that they watch YouTube videos for just less than a minute every day, and 40% of students claimed that they spend 30 minutes to one hour watching YouTube videos every day whereas, only 4 students declared that they watch YouTube videos for more than two hours daily. 8% of students maintained that they spend one to two hours doing the same. It is evident from the results that the students are utilizing the social media website- YouTube which is claimed to be very useful in enhancing students' listening skills. Less than half of the students hardly spend 30 minutes in one day on YouTube. Either they do not know about the positive effects of YouTube on the language skills of utilizers or they are least interested in enhancing their language skills, especially listening skills.

Chart Description: Types of YouTube Videos that Students Watch

	Frequency	Percent
Educational tutorials	16	16
Entertainment and humor	50	50
News and current events	12	12
Product reviews	4	4
Music Videos	8	8
Both educational and entertainment	10	10

This question deals with the types of videos that students watch on YouTube. Answers show that the students prefer to watch YouTube exhibit that only half of the participants watch entertainment videos on YouTube, and only 16% prefer to use YouTube for educational purposes; however, only 10% claimed that they use YouTube both for educational and non-educational purposes. Some students conveyed that they utilize social media to watch music videos (8%), news and current events (12%) and product reviews (4%). The results depict that most students do not utilize YouTube for educational purposes and only less than half watch entertainment videos on YouTube. Many students do not spend much time watching YouTube videos, if they rarely watch, they watch with objectives other than academic purposes such as developing their language skills or clarifying their academic concepts.

Chart Description: Purpose of Watching YouTube Videos

	Frequency	Percent
Yes, exclusively	28	28
Yes, but with a combination of other channels	44	44
No, I use other methods exclusively	8	8
No, I do not use YouTube for language learning	18	18

The results declare that only 28% of students which is just a small number informed that they watch YouTube videos to enhance their language skills; however, only 44% claimed that they watch channels related to language learning in combination with other channels. Some students accepted that they utilize other methods of English language skills development (8%) and others sustained that they do not use YouTube to develop their English language skills (18%). It is evident from the results that most of the students do not prefer to incorporate YouTube to develop their English language skills. If the students are not utilizing this useful source to develop their English Language skills, listening skills specifically, it would be difficult to expect that YouTube would have a positive impact on their language skills. Due to this underpinning factor, the rate of correlation showed a very weak positive correlation coefficient (0.038) and non-significant correlation (0.706) proving that the two variables do not have any meaningful relationship.

Chart Description: Motivation for Watching YouTube Videos

	Frequency	Percent
Educational purposes	6	6
Entertainment	30	30
Staying informed about global news	8	8
language improvement	26	26
Social Connection	20	20
educational and entertainment both	10	10

Concerning students’ motivation related to watching YouTube videos, some students utilize YouTube videos for language improvement (26%) and only a small number of students i.e. 6% watch YouTube videos for other educational purposes. However, most of the students watch YouTube videos for non-academic purposes i.e. entertainment (30%), news videos (8%), and social connection (20%). Nevertheless, a few students (10%) accepted that they watch YouTube videos for educational and entertainment purposes. The results vividly show that most students do not utilize YouTube videos to develop their English language skills or for educational purposes. However, if they rarely watch YouTube, they have some objectives other than those related to academics. All these evidences make it clear that the students are not inclined to use this wonderful resource for their language and educational development which has a strong negative impact on the results of this study.

VAK Learning Style Inventory Survey Results

Chart Description Learning Styles of Students

	Frequency	Percent
Visual	44	44
Auditory	36	36
Kinesthetic	14	14
Combination	6	6

Regarding the learning style test attempted by the students, less than half i.e. only 44% of students were visual learners and 36% of them were auditory learners; however, 14% had kinesthetic learning style whereas only a small number of students i.e. (6%) had a combination learning style which is a blend of two learning styles. It is interpreted from the results that most of the students had visual and auditory learning styles. Despite YouTube being compatible and aligned with their learning styles, the students did not prefer to spend more time watching YouTube videos. They were neither motivated nor inclined to watch YouTube videos for academic or non-academic purposes. This is evident from the weak negative correlational statistics generated from SPSS software - 0.083 and non-significant correlation, high p-value (0.414). It can be stated that an individual’s learning style does not affect the intensity of watching YouTube videos. It will not motivate students to utilize YouTube for educational or non-educational purposes. However, the studies conducted on the consideration of learning styles in the teaching-learning process enhance the effectiveness of the input.

The students grasp the concept more easily and deeply if they get involved with the activities according to their learning styles (REF). In this current study, the intensity of watching YouTube videos is very low and students rarely practice it in their daily routine. Therefore, the students did not fairly utilize YouTube even if it was well aligned with their specific learning styles. Hence, the students’ low use of YouTube has negatively affected the

study results. Since this research has been conducted with integrity and authenticity, the researcher would not be hindered in publishing the genuine results and interpretation of the study. It can be stated that if the students claimed to be frequent users of YouTube, the results might have been opposite to the current outcomes.

IELTS Listening Test Results

Chart Description: Listening Proficiency Level of Students

	Frequency	Percent
Non-User	24	24
Extremely Limited User	42	42
Modest User	30	30
Competent User	4	4

According to the listening proficiency test, most students showed very weak listening proficiency levels as 42% of students fell into the category ‘Extremely Limited Users’; however, only 4% were ‘Competent Users’. 30% of students were ‘Modest Users’ and 24% fell into the category ‘non-Users’. Through the results of the study, it is evident that the underpinning factor behind the poor proficiency level of the students and the weak positive correlation between the listening proficiency level and the intensity of watching YouTube videos is that most of the students rarely use YouTube videos either for academic or non-academic purposes. It can be stated that the positive correlation shows that if the students incorporate watching YouTube videos into their daily routine, YouTube has a positive impact on their listening skills. This happens as the students rarely benefit from it; therefore, they have weak listening skills. It is evident that by increasing the intensity of watching YouTube videos, the students can polish their English language skills, specifically, listening skills.

Explanation and Interpretation

The quantitative data collected through listening proficiency test, survey questionnaire, and learning style were analyzed using SPSS software, and correlation among all three variables was calculated step by step. The results were presented in tables generated by SPSS software and interpreted according to the correlation found.

Correlation between Learning Styles and Intensity of Watching YouTube Videos

		Intensity of Watching YouTube Videos
Learning Style	Pearson Correlation	-0.083
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.414

The results of the Pearson Correlation coefficient conducted between the intensity of watching YouTube videos and the students’ learning styles is -0.083 which reveals a negative correlation of -0.083 and the p-value of the correlation is 0.414. A value of 0.083 shows a very weak negative linear relationship between the variables. Since the p-value 0.414 is much greater than 0.05 and has failed to reject the study’s null hypothesis. This depicts that the relationship between the two variables is not statistically significant. A weak inverse relationship between the intensity of watching YouTube videos and the student’s learning styles has been noticed. If one variable increases the other variable is inclined to decrease. Nevertheless, the relationship is quite weak so it is nearly negligible. The high p-value of 0.414 shows that any noticed relationship between the intensity of watching YouTube videos and the learning styles of students can be by chance instead of an actual existing relationship or it can be stated that there is no significant relationship between the two variables. Therefore, it is said that the student’s learning styles do not impact the intensity of watching YouTube videos.

Correlations between Listening Proficiency Level and Intensity of Watching YouTube Videos

		Intensity of Watching YouTube Videos
Listening Proficiency Level	Pearson Correlation	.038
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.706

According to the results of the Pearson Correlation analysis conducted to examine the relationship between the intensity of watching YouTube videos and the student’s learning styles is 0.38 which reveals a weak positive linear correlation between these variables. Since the p-value 0.706 is much greater than 0.05, we have failed to reject the study’s null hypothesis. This depicts that the relationship between the two variables is not statistically significant. There is a weak direct relationship between the intensity of watching YouTube videos and the listening proficiency level of students. If one variable increases, the other variable also increases. Nevertheless, the relationship is quite weak so it is nearly negligible. The high p-value of 0.706 shows that any noticed relationship between the intensity of watching YouTube videos and the listening proficiency level of students can be by chance instead of an actual

existing relationship or it can be stated that there is no significant relationship between the two variables. Therefore, it is said that the intensity of watching YouTube videos does not impact the listening proficiency level of students.

Discussion

The results of this research demonstrate YouTube's enormous potential as a tool for improving listening skills as also suggested by Figo et al. (2025) through their experimental study that using YouTube and other digital platforms like this significantly impact students' listening skills. The findings; however, show that students use the site minimally, with the majority largely utilizing it for entertainment rather than education. Increased exposure to pertinent information may significantly impact language learning outcomes, as seen by the small positive association between the intensity of YouTube video watching and listening and competence levels. This is consistent with earlier studies which recommend the effectiveness of using multimedia for language learning. Additionally, the research discovered a statistically negligible negative relationship between students' YouTube video-watching intensity and their learning styles. This suggests that students' use of YouTube for language learning is not significantly influenced by their preferred learning methodology, kinesthetic, visual, or aural. Rather, structured usage, encouragement, and direction might be more important. The successful use of YouTube as a language learning tool seems to be significantly hampered by a lack of enthusiasm and poor knowledge about the platform's educational advantages.

The results indicate that more research is necessary to fully understand the elements including students' self-directed learning habits, technological availability, motivation, and monitored YouTube use. These factors could offer a more thorough comprehension of how to promote the instructional value of multimedia sites such as YouTube. Teachers and educational institutions should consider incorporating YouTube-based activities into their curricula to cope with these difficulties. Teachers may promote more intentional use of YouTube to enhance listening skills by offering students structured coaching and raising awareness. Future studies might examine the impact of these other factors to create more potent plans for using multimedia resources in language instruction.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that there is a positive correlation between students' intensity of watching YouTube videos and their listening proficiency level. However, a negative correlation has been found between students' learning styles and the intensity of watching YouTube videos. In addition to that, the correlation is insignificant as the students have rarely been watching YouTube videos. According to the results of this study, YouTube has a positive impact on developing students' listening skills. The students can improve their listening skills by watching YouTube videos more frequently. However, the students' learning styles do not play any role in motivating students to watch YouTube videos. To sum up, it can be stated that YouTube videos are effective for all students with different learning styles. Considering the results of this study, the researcher recommends students spend more time watching YouTube in English to develop their English Language skills. Moreover, it is recommended that ESL teachers integrate English YouTube videos in their classroom instruction and provide more guidance regarding the effectiveness, and ease-to-use of social media websites/tools as it would help the students gain learner autonomy and develop metacognitive skills.

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